

The study of HCl penetration behavior inside of an unsaturated polyester resin under temperature gradient to simulate the accidental roof failure of FRP outdoor storage tank containing high concentration HCl solution

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ABSTRACT

Isophthalic unsaturated polyester has a superior corrosion resistance and excellent chemical resistance which is extensively used as matrix for FRP composite material such as chemical storage tanks. Accidental failures of a FRP chemical tank roof were reported after the tank had been in service (outdoor) less than its expected lifetime. Therefore, an investigation of material's durability over a wide range of temperatures is significantly important. By using cyclic temperature of a solution condition, specimen is exposed into a chemical and the temperature is changed, a specimen in a liquid phase may change temperature along with the liquid; however, when a specimen is subjected in a vapor phase, the specimen may not change temperature with the vapor causing temperature difference at its surface and also inside of the material. Using cyclic temperature of solution condition in different chemicals (water, HCl and H₂SO₄), the strength of material in the vapor phase slightly decreased lower than the strength of material in the liquid phase and even lower than the strength of materials under isothermal at 80°C. In general, exposure to cyclic temperature of solution can influence the distributions of temperature and moisture concentration inside the material, which affects the performance of the material.

To understand the mechanism of the distribution of temperature, new experiment has been prepared by attaching two different temperatures of 35 mass% HCl solutions at each surfaces of iso-unsaturated polyester resin for several weeks. After analyzing flexural property, the strength of material significantly decreased about 50% for 4 weeks under temperature gradient condition at 20°C and 50°C. Cross section after cutting by blade machine were examined by SEM along with EDS. Cl element mapping by EDS on the cross section of specimen under isothermal at 40°C and 50°C already reached an equilibrium level within 4 weeks. This study has emphasized to develop a step towards the roof failure of chemical tank which was affected by the temperature fluctuate by the outdoor environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Production of Fiber Reinforced Plastic (FRP) is a rapidly growing industry with many applications in chemical plant field. Because of their corrosion resistance, FRPs are often used to construct corrosive chemical storage tanks, piping, scrubbers, beams, gratings and other components for use in corrosive environments. The potential cost saving associated with replacing steel pipes with FRP made with polyester or vinylester are considerable. Comparing to metallic material, FRP possess a higher chemical durability and lighter weight which is advantageous when used as a chemical storage tank or chemical vessel for transportation containing severe chemical solutions, such as hydrochloric acid or sulfuric acid.

In general, FRP combines the widely divergent properties of its constituents – reinforcing fibers and resin – into a unique material. Reinforcing fibers contribute virtually all of the material's strength; on

the other hand resin provides most of a corrosion resistance property. The most commonly used thermosetting resin systems for corrosion resistance material are vinyl ester resin, isophthalic polyester resin and *etc.* The corrosion barrier is dedicated to resisting surface corrosion and to preventing the process environment from permeating into the structural material. A good corrosion barrier is necessary to protect the structural material from the effect of permeation by process fluids.

Durability of FRP applications is very important to ensure the lifetime of it from the point of view of the end-users. Some accidents have been reported where the FRP chemical tank containing hydrochloric acid has failed at the roof. These failures have occurred within a much shorter time period than the expected service life. Many studies on the mechanical effects of polymer degradation have been reported in the literatures [1-18]. In most cases these studies show the change in mechanical properties of matrix.

The main factors of investigations carried out onto this failure are, time of exposure, concentration of solution, and temperature of solution under isothermal conditions, temperature gradient condition and their effects on solution diffusion into corrosion barrier layer or polymeric material. Many researchers reported that materials in the liquid phase of the solution would suffer more severe conditions than those in the vapor phase. The previous study of the accelerated failure of material in water, hydrochloric acid (volatile acid) solution, sulfuric acid (non-volatile acid) solution also proposed that the strength of the material in the liquid phase was more damaging than the vapor phase [19-21].

The accidental failures of rooftops of FRP chemical tanks were contrary to the expectations from the previous studies. Therefore, comprehensive study into the material durability over a wide range of temperatures and more severe conditions is required. Temperature changes between day and night should be considered and this factor could result in a dynamic condition in the vapor phase that is expected to cause the failure of chemical tank. Gases will start to evaporate at a higher temperature, and then condense into a liquid at a lower temperature. At the dew point of the saturated condition, vapors will start to condense and can be observed near the surface of the material. The absorbed solution in a polymer network may also dew where a temperature difference occurs. Since the vapor phase is more sensitive than that of the liquid phase to the temperature change during the day, the temperature fluctuations are considered that could lead to a failure of the chemical tank's roof.

2 LITERARY REVIEW

The study of the unsaturated polyester resin in 20 mass% HCl under isothermal condition and cyclic solution was investigated [20]. The results showed that the rate of mass uptake under 80°C isothermal condition was higher than cyclic temperature condition, as shown in Fig. 1. A heating/cooling ratio of cyclic solution temperature was fluctuated between 40°C to 80°C every 1 hour for 12 hours and kept at 20°C for 12 hours. Mean temperature of cyclic solution temperature condition is 40°C, which is two times lower than the temperature of isothermal condition. The strength of unsaturated polyester resin under 80°C isothermal condition in the liquid phase slightly decreased and was lower than the specimen in the vapor phase. In contrast, the strength of specimen in the vapor phase under cyclic solution temperature was slightly lower than the specimen in the liquid phase. The results of cyclic temperature solution were an interesting point to observed fracture surface of the specimen in the vapor phase. From SEM observation, microvoids were observed in white layer near the surface inside the specimen, as shown in Fig. 3 and 4.

Hence, we aim to extend the investigation of previous study. Since the temperature of the vapor phase is sensitive which causes temperature difference between the temperature of material at surface and inner area of specimen when temperature changes. We designed new experiment to force two different temperatures at each surface of specimen to analyze the effect of temperature distribution and HCl distribution on material property. Material property was determined by using three points bending. The most common methods to analysis chemical composition of material are Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS).

Figure 1: The results of mass uptake of unsaturated polyester resin at 20 mass% HCl in the liquid phase and the vapor phase under 80°C isothermal (left) and cyclic solution temperature condition (right).

Figure 2: The results of mechanical property of unsaturated polyester resin after exposed at 20 mass% HCl in the liquid phase and the vapor phase under 80°C (left) and cyclic solution temperature condition (right).

Figure 3: The white layer from the cross-section surface of unsaturated polyester resin at 20 mass% HCl in the vapor phase under cyclic solution temperature condition.

Figure 4: Microvoids in white layer at higher magnification.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

A specimen of unsaturated polyester was prepared by mixing Iso-phthalic acid type unsaturated polyester resin with cobalt naphthenate (Rigolac 2141B) with Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide (MEKP). The ratio of resin and MEKP was 100:1. A mixing procedure was 600 rpm for 2 minutes following by de-gas process for 10 minutes. A curing method was 50°C for 6 hours and 100°C for 6 hours. After finishing the curing procedure to make 2 mm thick plate, the specimen was prepared with the dimension of 25 x 60 x 2 mm, and then dried at 50°C for 10 days to ensure that the remaining moisture was removed and the weight was not changed before carried out experiments. The shape and dimension of the specimen is shown in Fig. 5. On the other hand, the size of specimen for temperature gradient experiment is larger, as shown in Fig.6.

Figure 5: A dimension of specimen for isothermal condition.

Figure 6: A dimension of specimen for temperature gradient condition.

3.2 CONDITIONING SOLUTION TEMPERATURE

In this paper we focus on two testing conditions: (1) Isothermal condition at 40°C and 50°C and (2) Temperature gradient condition. Hydrochloric acid was prepared at 35 mass% HCl.

3.2.1 ISOTHERMAL CONDITION

For the isothermal condition, the solution temperature was held constant via the use of a water bath. A glass container contained a solution and specimens. Specimens were supported by fluororesin tubes in both liquid and vapor phase, as shown in Fig.7.

Figure 7: A water bath for controlling temperature.

2.2.2 TEMPERATURE GRADIENT CONDITION

Temperature gradient test was conducted with the set-up of special glass vessels shown in Fig. 8 and 9. A specimen is put between the vessel one side contains 35 mass% HCL solution at 20°C and 50°C. The cooling water at 20°C flows around the glass vessel containing HCl at 20°C.

Figure 8: Schematic apparatus of temperature gradient test.

Figure 9: Setup for temperature gradient testing by glass vessels both side contain 35 mass% HCl at 20°C with cooling water and 50°C with heating ribbon outside.

3.3 MASS UPTAKE EQUATION

To measure the mass uptake, each specimen was removed from the environmental conditioning chamber, and then wiped off before measuring weight change. The moisture uptake or percent weight gain was calculated by Eq. (1).

$$\text{Mass uptake (\%)} = (W_t - W_0) / W_0 \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_t = Weight of specimen at time t

W_0 = Weight of specimen at initial time

3.4 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Flexural properties; elastic modulus and strength were used to examine the mechanical properties of the ageing sample at different time according to ASTM D790 (by Shimadzu Autograph AGS-1KNJ machine, cross-head speed at 2 mm/min). Flexural tests were performed at room temperature after specimens were placed in a room for approximately 4 hours therefore allowing the temperature to adjust and settle.

3.5 MORPHOLOGY OBSERVATION

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is used as a method of studying fracture surface morphology. After performing the bending test, a cross-section of specimen was examined by SEM. EDS is used to find the chemical composition of materials and to create element composition maps over a much broader raster area. Together, these capabilities provide fundamental compositional information for a wide variety of materials.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

4.1 The percentage of the mass uptake under isothermal condition

The result of the mass uptake of specimen immersed into the solution under isothermal condition 40°C and 50°C is shown in Fig.10. To measure the changes of mass, each specimen was removed from the environmental conditioning chamber, weighed quickly using a precise balance and then returned to chamber. From the results, it can be seen that the mass uptake still increased even it was exposed almost 3 months. The percentage of mass uptake of specimen under 50°C is higher than 40°C. Also, the percentage of mass uptake of specimen under the liquid phase is higher than the vapor phase.

These experimental results show good agreement with previous studies under isothermal condition [19-21].

Figure 10 : Mass uptake of specimen under isothermal condition at 40°C and 50°C.

4.2 Mechanical Properties

The result of flexural property is shown in Fig. 11. The strength of material analyzing by 3 points bending under 50°C isothermal condition is lower than the specimen under isothermal temperature at 40°C. It can be seen that the strength decreased at an early immersion time and reach a stable level even exposure time was around 3 months. On the other hand, the chemical did not affect the modulus of specimen immersed in HCl solution at isothermal condition 40°C and 50°C in the liquid phase and the vapor phase. From the experimental result at isothermal condition 40°C and 50°C, it provided long-term experimental results up to 2100 hours, however; the strength of the specimen did not affect as we expected from the evidence of the accident failure of FRP chemical tank. By analyzing mechanical property of roof material and wall material of the broken FRP chemical tank, the strength of the roof material was 50% lower than the strength of wall material. In addition, the previous study of mechanical property of unsaturated polyester resin in 25 mass% HCl at 80°C is also shown in Fig.12 and 13. Retention of the strength at higher exposure time of unsaturated polyester resin under 20 mass% HCl at 80°C and under 35 mass% HCl at 40°C and 50°C indicated that the decrease of the strength was not a large number.

In previous studies, we had introduced new experimental method, cyclic solution temperature method to accelerate the degradation of unsaturated polyester. The experiment showed that the strength of the specimen in the vapor phase under cyclic temperature slightly decreased to be lower than the strength of specimen in the liquid phase, as shown in Fig. 2. It assumed that the temperature in the vapor phase is very sensitive which can change rapidly when temperature changes. In general, when temperature reduction from outside of the tank occurs in the vapor phase, dew condensation can be observed. It is due to temperature near the surface and environmental temperature is different. At the same time, temperature distribution also occurs inside of the specimen, which is expected to affect the state of penetrated liquid.

From this assumption, we design new experimental test to force temperature distribution to occur inside the specimen by applying two different temperatures at each surface of specimen, as shown in Fig. 9.

The experimental results of unsaturated polyester resin under temperature gradient condition showed in Fig. 14, the strength of specimen under temperature gradient experiment at 50°C and 20°C for 720 hours decreased about 50% of the strength of neat resin. These results can indicate an

important point of the effect of the temperature gradient on mechanical property of unsaturated polyester resin.

Figure 11: Flexural property of unsaturated polyester resin under isothermal condition at 40°C and 50°C of 35 mass% HCl.

Figure 12: Retention of the strength of unsaturated polyester resin in the vapor phase under isothermal condition 35 mass% at 50°C, 40°C and under 20 mass% at 80°C.

Figure 13: Retention of the strength of unsaturated polyester resin in the liquid phase under isothermal condition 35 mass% at 50°C, 40°C and under 20 mass% at 80°C.

Figure 14: Retention of the strength of unsaturated polyester resin in the liquid phase under 35 mass% at 50°C, 40°C and under 20 mass% at 80°C.

3.3 Morphology observation

SEM and EDS was used to observe the cross-section surface of the specimen exposed under temperature gradient condition and isothermal conditions after analyzing the mechanical properties. The surface was carefully polished by sandpaper before examined by SEM/EDS.

In Fig. 15, the specimen immersed for enough time under temperature gradient condition showed that line analysis of Cl can be observed with higher level of Cl element from 50°C. In addition, the mapping of Cl element can also detect in the specimen under 40°C and 50°C isothermal condition. However, the Cl element could not be detected in the specimen in 20 mass% HCl at 80°C. We guess the specimen immersed into HCl solution between 20 mass% HCl to 35 mass% HCl could detect the Cl element which will be the future work.

From higher magnification of cross-section surface of specimen under temperature gradient condition, holes or microvoids can only be observed near the surface of specimen. In Fig. 16, for example, microvoids can detect near the surface inside of the specimen.

Figure 15: SEM and EDS observations of specimen under temperature gradient 50°C -20°C for 4 weeks.

Figure 16: A higher magnification to observe microvoids in the red line of specimen under temperature gradient 50°C -20°C for 4 weeks.

5 DISCUSSION

In general, the FRP chemical tanks are also used to contain various chemicals, such as sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid or water. However, FRP chemical tanks containing high HCl solution were only reported the failure of the roof. The phenomena are still not fully understood and the investigations still go on. In our previous work, the study of unsaturated polyester resin exposed under water solution and sulfuric acid had been already reported. One of important results to assume the accident failure of roof material of FRP chemical tank containing 35 mass% HCl can be explained by a size of polymer network and a size of molecule of water, sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid molecule. Basically, a hydrochloric acid molecule has smaller size than water and sulfuric acid, which can easily penetrate into polymer network.

In Fig.17, the mass uptake of unsaturated polyester resin under water solution at 80°C, 20 mass% H₂SO₄ at 80°C, 20 mass% at 80°C, 35 mass% at 50°C and 35 mass% at 40°C indicated that the percentage of mass uptake at maximum level of H₂SO₄ solution was very low, comparing with water solution and HCl. Since a molecule size of H₂SO₄ is bigger than water and HCl, which could not penetrate through polymer network, but water does, so the chemical attack from H₂SO₄ might not significantly affect the property of material. On the other hand, the mass uptake of the HCl showed that it has not reached to a saturation level and still increase with increasing exposure time since the molecule size of HCl is quite small which can further penetrated into polymer network. Hence, the chemical attack to the polymer network can take place, which significantly affect the property of material.

Figure 17 : The results of mass uptake of unsaturated polyester resin under water solution at 80°C, 20 mass% H₂SO₄ at 80°C, 20 mass% at 80°C, 35 mass% at 50°C and 35 mass% at 40°C.

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